

Role of Women in Politics with Respect to Female Leadership Qualities

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Abstract

Women are one of the best managers and leaders in the most challenging situations it is proved that women handle any situation in very calm and best possible way then men. Women demonstrate political leadership by working across party lines through parliamentary women's caucuses—even in the most politically combative environments—and by championing issues of gender equality, such as the elimination of gender-based violence, parental leave and childcare, pensions, gender-equality laws, From the local to the global level, women's leadership and political participation are restricted. Women are underrepresented as voters, as well as in leading positions, whether in elected office, the civil service, the private sector or academia. This occurs despite their proven abilities as leaders and agents of change, and their right to participate equally in democratic governance.

Women face several obstacles to participating in political life. Structural barriers through discriminatory laws and institutions still limit women's options to run for office. Capacity gaps mean women are less likely than men to have the education, contacts and resources needed to become effective leaders. This paper is decent contribution in creating awareness about women leadership in brief to readers.

Keywords: Women , Politics , Parliament , Gender ,Confidence , Effective.

1. Introduction

The best way to make the women powerful is to give them power and make them more free and provide fair and equal opportunities. Generally, effective leaders should have the following personality traits: **self-confidence, responsibility, energy, innovation, the ability to solve interpersonal tensions, accept the consequences of their decisions, have temerity, and take the initiative in social situations** Page | 2

Women in positions of power are women who hold an occupation that gives them great authority, influence and responsibility. Historically, power has been distributed among the sexes disparately. Power and powerful positions have most often been associated with men as opposed to women. As gender equality increases, women hold more and more powerful positions. Accurate and proportional representation of women in social systems has been shown to be important to the long-lasting success of the human race. Additionally, a study shows that "absence is not merely a sign of disadvantage and disenfranchisement, but the exclusion of women from positions of power also compounds gender stereotypes and retards the pace of equalization"

2. Gender as a Factor

Positions of power and gender are very intertwined. As one study pointed out, "Power differences frequently underlie what appear to be gender differences in behavior; as society is currently configured, power and gender are never independent". As such, gender relates to power in the different ways power is acquired, used, and manifested. A 1988 journal article summarizes this relation between gender and power: "the idea that women and men differ in power motivation is reinforced by history and culture. In the history of the west, certainly, women have had less access to most forms of power than have men. Many people believe that men are interested in power and getting power while women are not. Others hold that men and women differ in the ways that they establish, maintain and express power". Additionally, studies have shown that increasing women's participation in leadership positions decreases corruption, as "women are less involved in bribery, and are less likely to condone bribe taking". A study on gender and corruption from 2000 also found that "cross-country data show that corruption is less severe where women hold a larger share of parliamentary seats and senior positions in the government bureaucracy, and comprise a larger share of the labor force".

3. Women in government

For many years and in most regions of the globe, politics had not allowed women to play a significant role in government. Even in the early 1900s, politics were viewed almost exclusively as the domain of men. However, women's movements and culture-changing events such as World War II gradually increased women's rights and roles in politics. Many factors go into the degree of female participation in governments across the world. One 1999 study found: "The electoral system structure, left party government, the timing of women's suffrage, the share of women in professional occupations, and cultural attitudes toward the role of women in politics each play a role in accounting for variation in the degree of gender inequality in political representation around the world. Even still, there are many other factors that play a serious role in female participation in government. There is a significant "perceived liability" to a party of having a female candidate for office, according to a 2005 study. Even today, no country in the world has 50% or higher female participation in a national legislature, and 73% of countries have less than 20% female participation. There are multiple levels of power positions in the government from the local level to the national level. Accordingly, there are different degrees to which women partake in these different levels. For example, studies have found in India that "large scale membership of women in local councils" can be more effective in exerting influence, such as over crime rates, than "their presence in higher level leadership positions". However, it is important to have women at all levels of government to ensure the representation as well as enacting of women's interests.

4. Six Qualities of Effective Women Leaders

- A belief in oneself. ...
- A willingness to nurture. ...
- A focus on achieving one's goals. ...
- Building and leading teams. ...
- Willingness to question the status quo. ...
- Not afraid to ask for help

5. Women and Leadership

The worldwide many women are taking the responsibility of State and country as whole in managing the best possible way all the issues and problems faced by the country. Some of the women leaders have brought more positive change in the country as shown in the picture below.

PROMINENT LEADERS

SOURCE :-[HTTPS://WWW.GOOGLE.COM/SEARCH?Q=BEST+WOMEN+LEADERS+](https://www.google.com/search?q=best+women+leaders+)

6. Skills successful women leaders use to stand out.

- Emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and manage our own emotions, and those of others around us. ...
- Creativity and innovation. ...
- Strategic thinking. ...
- Confidence. ...
- Trustworthiness. ...
- Problem-solving. ...
- Persistence. ...
- Collaboration.

7. Difference between Women and Men Leadership

Women tend to have a more cooperative, participatory style of leading. Men tend to have a more “command and control style,” according to the American Psychological Association. They're more task-oriented and directive, while women are more democratic.

8. Disadvantage of Women Leadership

- Weaker Sex. Although this is not true especially nowadays, some still consider women fragile and dependent on men when it comes to manly chores and activities. ...
- Emotional. ...
- Prone to Sexual Harassment. ...
- Health issue if any ...
- Complicated Labor and Pregnancy.
- Family Responsibility

9. Conclusion

The Women leadership is best to make any country developed and have maximum use of women potential and best qualities of women leadership. In the present days many women take active part in politics and prove that they can also make the positive change in the political environment of the country. The author has done decent contribution in making this important topic of women leadership for the benefit of the leaders and readers.

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